

FINAL REPORT

SPOKE 1: MOUNTAIN INNOVATION ECOSYSTEM

PROJECT NAME: HOW MOUNTAIN COMPANIES RESPOND TO DISRUPTIONS: THE ROLE OF SUPPLY CHAIN STRUCTURE

The Final Report relates to the scientific activities carried out and the results achieved within the project funded through the Young Researcher Call for Proposals: it must provide a comprehensive description of the project results, with specific reference to the project activities carried out, the progress made and the achievement of the milestones and targets set out in the approved project.

The Final Report is submitted by the PI (principal investigator) and is evaluated by the Scientific Committee, in accordance with the provisions of the aforementioned Call for Proposals.

The Final Report must underscore these aspects:

- the final objectives achieved and set out in the project submitted for evaluation, as well as any deviations from the established objectives and the reasons for such deviations;
- any deviations between the approved Economic and Financial Plan and the reported costs, that must be justified.

PROJECT DETAILS	
Spoke	1 – Mountain Innovation Ecosystem
PROJECT ACRONYM	MoDiSC
PI – Principal Investigator - University	Margherita Molinaro – Faculty of Engineering / Competence Centre for Mountain Innovation Ecosystems – Free University of Bozen-Bolzano
Starting date:	04/10/2024
Duration:	13 months
Ending date:	31/10/2025
<i>Other participants university</i>	- Mehari Beyene Teshome – Competence Centre for Mountain Innovation Ecosystems – Free University of Bozen-Bolzano

Annexes:

<i>Possible annex</i>	-
<i>Possible annex</i>	-

Date: 09.02.2026

PI signature: *Margherita Molinaro*

1. Technical and scientific results of the project

1.1. Description of the final results achieved

Maximum two pages.

Images and diagrams may be attached at the end of the report. Indicate whether the expected results were achieved, explaining and quantifying any deviations.

Describe the expected and actual results of the project in qualitative terms.

Project objectives and overall approach

The project aimed to investigate whether and how firms located in mountain regions differ from non-mountain firms in terms of supply chain structure, and how these structural characteristics relate to firms' capacity to cope with disruptions. The project originally pursued two main research objectives: (i) to compare the supply chain structures of mountain and non-mountain firms, and (ii) to analyse how supply chain structure affects the resilience of mountain firms through an event study of disruptive episodes. To address these objectives, the project adopted a multi-method research design combining an in-depth literature review, large-scale secondary data collection, quantitative analysis of supply chain networks, and the development of a practical assessment tool for firms operating in mountain regions.

Results achieved

The core scientific contribution of the project consists in a detailed and original empirical analysis of the supply chain structures of firms located in mountain regions compared to a matched sample of non-mountain firms. This activity builds on a substantial data infrastructure effort that represents, in itself, a significant project outcome.

Following an extensive literature review (WP1), which identified the most relevant structural dimensions of supply chains for firm resilience and highlighted the limited empirical evidence on the role of firm location in supply chain design, the project focused on the construction of a novel longitudinal dataset combining multiple data sources (WP2). Buyer-supplier relationships were reconstructed using the *FactSet Supply Chain Relationships* database, covering a time span of ten years. These data were complemented with firm-level financial and demographic information extracted from *Orbis*. The integration and harmonisation of these databases required extensive data cleaning, matching, and validation activities. Overall, this process resulted in an unbalanced panel dataset with approximately 5,600 firms observed over up to ten years, corresponding to a total of 32,259 firm-year observations.

Firm headquarters of the 5,600 firms were geolocated using GPS coordinates and mapped against an established mountain classification framework. This procedure allowed the identification of firms operating in mountain regions (n=121). A control group of non-mountain firms was then constructed using a matching strategy based on industry, country and firm size. The final analytical sample consists of 242 firms, half of which are classified as mountain.

Based on the resulting dataset, the project analysed supply chain structure along multiple dimensions, both upstream (suppliers) and downstream (customers). In line with the theoretical framework developed through the literature review, three main dimensions were considered:

- *Horizontal complexity*, measured as the number of first-tier suppliers (and customers);
- *Vertical complexity*, captured by the average number of second-tier suppliers per first-tier supplier (and analogously for customers);
- *Spatial complexity*, measured as the number of countries in which first-tier suppliers (and customers) are located.

The empirical analysis (WP3) revealed clear differences between mountain and non-mountain firms. Contrary to initial expectations, firms located in mountain regions exhibit significantly higher horizontal complexity, both upstream and downstream, compared to their non-mountain counterparts. In other words, mountain firms tend to maintain a broader base of direct suppliers and customers. This result suggests that firms operating in geographically constrained and risk-prone environments may adopt more diversified supply chain structures as a strategic response to contextual uncertainty.

The finding is particularly relevant as it challenges the conventional assumption that remoteness and infrastructural constraints necessarily lead to simpler or more localised supply chains. Instead, the results indicate that mountain firms may compensate for environmental and logistical vulnerabilities by spreading dependencies across a larger number of partners. These insights contribute to the

literature on supply chain design and resilience by highlighting the role of geographical context as a driver of structural adaptation. The preliminary results of these analyses were presented at international scientific conferences and a scientific journal paper is in course of submission to an international journal (WP5).

Deviation from the original plan

While the comparative analysis of supply chain structures between mountain and non-mountain firms was fully implemented, the event study originally planned to analyse firm performance responses to specific disruptive events was not completed but replaced with an alternative methodology (see below). This deviation is primarily attributable to two interrelated factors. First, the acquisition and processing of large-scale supply chain data required substantially more time than initially anticipated. The delayed access to the FactSet database, combined with the complexity of reconstructing longitudinal buyer-supplier networks and merging them with financial and geographical data, led to a necessary reallocation of project effort toward ensuring data quality and methodological robustness. Second, the empirical identification of disrupted mountain firms revealed limitations in sample size, as the number of mountain firms for which both disruption-related information and sufficiently rich supply chain data were simultaneously available proved to be smaller than expected.

Rather than conducting an event study on a limited and potentially underpowered sample, the project prioritised the completion of a solid and reliable structural analysis of supply chains. This choice allowed the project to deliver robust empirical evidence on the structural preconditions that may support resilience in mountain contexts, laying a sound foundation for future extensions of the research. Insights from the literature on supply chain resilience were therefore used to interpret the observed structural patterns and to link supply chain complexity to firms' potential capacity to absorb and adapt to disruptions. In this sense, the project achieved the underlying objective of advancing the understanding of resilience in mountain regions, albeit through a refined and more foundational analytical perspective.

Practical implications and assessment tool development

Building on the empirical results and theoretical insights generated by the project, a functional prototype of a Supply Chain Resilience Assessment Tool for mountain firms was developed (WP4). The tool translates the key dimensions of supply chain structure analysed in the project into a benchmarking framework that allows firms to compare their own supply chain configuration with that of similar firms operating in comparable contexts.

The tool enables companies to input basic information about their supply chain structure and sector, and to receive an indicative assessment of their level of supply chain complexity relative to a reference group. Although simplified compared to the initial vision outlined in the proposal, the tool is fully consistent with the empirical evidence produced by the project and provides an accessible first step for self-assessment and awareness-building among mountain firms.

Overall, the project achieved its primary objective of generating new empirical knowledge on the impact supply chain structures on firm resilience in mountain regions and translating this knowledge into actionable insights for both scholars and practitioners. The results obtained constitute a solid basis for future research activities, including the extension of the analysis to disruption-specific event studies as additional data become available.

Highlight the starting and final TRL (Technology Readiness Level) and the main KPI (Key Performance Indicator) achieved

The project started at TRL 2, corresponding to the conceptual development of a research-based analytical framework, and concluded at TRL 3–4 with the implementation of a functional prototype of a Supply Chain Resilience Assessment Tool. Key Performance Indicators include the construction of an integrated dataset, the completion of the planned quantitative analyses, and the development of the prototype tool.

Describe the External Partners who collaborated, their contribution, and the possible synergies that may continue in the near future

During the project, a collaboration was established with a researcher from the University of Padova, focusing on methodological discussions and interpretations of empirical results. This collaboration supported the refinement of the analytical approach adopted and contributed to the validation of the research design. The interaction initiated during the project is expected to continue in the near future through joint research activities and potential co-authored publications on related topics.

1.2. Summary of deliverables

Name	Result ¹	Links	TRL ²	Description and references
	[SCI] [PROD] [SERV] [PROC] [BUS] [DSG] [METH] [PO]	Link to Zenodo or BIA	[TRL4] [TRL5] [TRL6] [TRL7] [TRL8] [N.A.]	[Publication] [Prototyping in laboratory environment] [Prototyping in production environment] [Pilot, demonstrator or test] [Intellectual property management] [Patent submission] [Other]
Abstract and conference presentation "Mountain location choices and supply chain structure: A secondary data analysis" <i>Teshome MB, Molinaro M, Podrecca M.</i>	SCI	https://hdl.handle.net/10863/47361	N.A.	Abstract accepted and presented at the 15th EDSI Annual Conference - Decision Making facing economic, environmental and social changes, Gothenburg, Sweden, June 1-4, 2025
Abstract and conference presentation "Mountain location choices and supply chain structure: A secondary data analysis" <i>Molinaro M, Teshome MB, Podrecca M.</i>	SCI	https://hdl.handle.net/10863/47368	N.A.	Abstract accepted and presented at the EurOMA 2025 Conference, Milan (Italy), 13th June – 18th June 2025
Abstract and conference presentation "The impact of mountain location on supply chain structure decisions" <i>Molinaro M, Teshome MB, Podrecca M.</i>	SCI	https://hdl.handle.net/10863/47369	N.A.	Abstract accepted and presented at ISIEA 2025 Conference, Bolzano (Italy), 18th June – 20th June 2025
Functional prototype Supply Chain Resilience Assessment Tool	SERV	Supply Chain Complexity Assessment t	TRL4	Functional prototype of a digital assessment tool that allows firms to input basic information on their supply chain structure and receive a benchmarking-based evaluation derived from the project's empirical results.

¹ [SCI — Scientific discovery, model, theory, etc.] [PROD — Product (new or improved)] [SERV — Service (new or improved)] [PROC — Industrial process (new or improved)] [BUS — Business model (new or improved)] [DSG — Design (new or improved)] [METH — Method, material, technology, design (new or improved)]

² [TRL4 - Technology validated in the laboratory] [TRL5 - Technology validated in the relevant environment] [TRL6 - Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment] [TRL7 - Demonstration of the prototype system in an operational environment] [TRL8 - Complete and qualified system] [TRL9 - Real system tested in an operational environment] [Not applicable]

2. COMPLIANCE WITH CONDITIONALITIES AND ALL ADDITIONAL REQUIREMENTS RELATED TO THE PNRR MEASURES

2.1. DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code

Description of how the activities carried out comply with the DNSH principle and legislation provided for by the Environmental Code. In this regard, the reasons why the activities carried out do not cause significant harm to each of the environmental objectives are reported.

Environment	Has the DNSH principle been respected for the environmental objective? (Y/N) ³	Justifications:
1. Climate change mitigation	Y	The project is based on data analysis and desk research activities and does not involve physical interventions, emissions, or energy-intensive processes.
2. Climate change adaptation	Y	The project does not involve activities exposed to climate-related physical risks and does not negatively affect climate adaptation capacities.
3. Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources	Y	The project does not involve the use of water resources or activities affecting marine or freshwater ecosystems.
4. Transition to a circular economy, including waste reduction and recycling	Y	The project does not generate waste or require the use of physical materials. All activities are conducted digitally, minimizing resource consumption.
5. Prevention and reduction of air, water or soil pollution	Y	The project does not involve emissions, discharges, or the use of polluting substances and therefore does not contribute to air, water, or soil pollution.
6. Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystem	Y	The project does not involve land use, construction, or activities affecting natural habitats, biodiversity, or ecosystems.

2.2. Consistency with the digital constraint

Max 500 characters

Describe how the activities carried out and the related expenses incurred contribute to the achievement of the digital constraint, thus promoting the digital transition and at the same time ensuring compliance with the contribution to the digital objective

The project contributes to the digital objective by relying on large-scale digital datasets and data-driven analytical methods to study supply chain structures. Project activities involved the acquisition, integration, and processing of digital supply chain and firm-level data, as well as geospatial analysis. Moreover, the development of a digital Supply Chain Resilience Assessment Tool translates research results into an accessible digital instrument, supporting firms' self-assessment and promoting the digital transition of decision-making processes.

³ If the activities carried out do not have an impact on the environmental objective, it is appropriate to answer "Yes", in case of "Not", enter the reasons in the "Justifications" column of the same table..

3. ECONOMICS RESULTS OF THE PROJECT

3.1. Project costs

Attach the final statement of costs incurred in connection with the project, indicating the type of cost incurred.

BUDGET			
	Final amount (€ - %)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
Costs for specialist consultancy services	0 € - 0%	7.000,00 € - 17.5%	The planned development activities were carried out internally by the research team rather than through external consultancy services. This resulted in no expenditure under this category, while fully achieving the intended development objectives.
Costs for materials, supplies and similar products	20.404,51 € - 90%	30.488,00 € - 75%	Expenditures under this category were lower than initially estimated due to cost-effective procurement of data and research resources. The activities originally planned under this category were fully implemented.
Mission expenses	2.314,72 € - 10%	3.000,00 € - 7.5%	Mission-related costs were lower than initially estimated due to efficient participation in conferences and events.
Total	22.719,23 €		

BUDGET			
	Final amount (€ - %)	Initial assignment (€ - %)	Justification of the change in expenditure for the purposes of the project
RI -	17.343,83 € - 76,3%	30.488,00 € - 75%	Research-related expenditures mainly include data acquisition and processing activities supporting the empirical analysis of supply chain structures.
SS -	5.375,40 € - 23,7%	10.000,00 € - 25%	Development-related expenditures include mission expenses for conferences and events, as well as a share (~15%) of data acquisition costs used for the design, calibration, and implementation of the Supply Chain Resilience Assessment Tool developed within the project.
Total	22.719,23 €		

4. SUMMARY OF TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC CHANGES TO THE PROJECT (IF ANY)

Summarise the technical and financial changes that have been made to the project. Please note that, according to the call for proposals, changes must not substantially alter the objectives, results and impact of the initial project and must not lead to an increase in total expenditure. Please also specify whether the changes have an impact on the balance between the different types of expenditure.

During the implementation of the project, limited technical and financial adjustments were introduced, without affecting the objectives, expected results, or overall impact of the initial proposal.

From a technical perspective, the Supply Chain Resilience Assessment Tool was developed internally by the research team rather than through an external consultancy service, as originally planned. This choice allowed close integration between the empirical research activities and the development phase, while ensuring flexibility and full control over data handling. From a financial perspective, this adjustment resulted in lower expenditures for specialist consultancy services and an overall under-utilisation of the approved budget.

Overall, the project was completed below the approved total budget. The adjustments did not alter the balance between research (RI) and development (SS) activities in functional terms.